

Senior Citizens Policies of Odisha, an Estimate

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Abstract

The present research study focuses on examining the senior citizens policy of Odisha and its estimation. It aims to explore how the voices and demands of senior citizens are reflected in public policies of state of Odisha. Senior citizens in Odisha are currently facing some major challenges, and the study seeks to analyze these issues in the context of the policies designed to address them. The objective of the senior citizens policy of Odisha is to minimize the challenges faced by this vulnerable section. Inadequate financial assistance and lack of social awareness are bottlenecking the effectiveness of policies in meeting the needs of senior citizens. Generation gap and rise of standard of living are responsible factors behind the problems of senior citizens. This paper also aims to highlight the need for the government for developing an extensive plan to expand financial assistance for elderly population, especially in the field of senior citizens policy and old age homes, which would greatly benefit the elderly. The study estimates the existing public policies for senior citizens in Odisha and examines their values. Additionally, it seeks to identify valuable remedies to the challenges faced by senior citizens. The methodology of this research is based on both primary and secondary data sources.

Key Words

Senior Citizens, Public Policy, Old Age Homes, Policy Estimation, Financial Assistance

Introduction

Senior citizens are valuable assets for our society building. They are directly affiliated with our culture, traditions and factors behind the success. Our parents are called living god and their blessings are needed each and every steps of life paths. Article 41 of Indian constitution under the Directive Principles of State Policies (DPSP) says about the welfare of the elderly population. Senior citizens torture, exploitation and harassment become prime debate of discussion in present era. Crimes against elderly are also increasing day by day within our state. According to the 2011 census, 9.5 percent of population of Odisha consists of the people over the age of sixty, in comparison with 8.6% in India. Many research resulted that in Odisha most of senior citizens are facing financial crises and unable to fulfil their fundamental requirements in our state. Many elderly have not connected with work related pensions or government assistance in Odisha. Different surveys showed that, Senior citizens are working for their

own maintenance and their numbers are probably 80 per cent. United Nations Populations Fund (UNPF) clears that, in Odisha one senior citizen is harassed out of the ten. In Angul district of Odisha, a sick elderly mother abandoned in jungle by her son and rescued by the local people (Nandighosha TV, 3 May 2025). This news shows the lack of humanity, morality and duties towards our parents. Due to financial insufficiency, property disputes and generation gap the elderly are facing many challenges. To abide by the moral rights and duties towards our older parents all should pay attention during their eleventh hour. Effective elderly welfare policies with sufficient financial assistance senior citizens could strengthen their rights and liberties. In Odisha, there needs to be an increase in numbers of old age homes for providing a free and secure life to the elderly. Researcher plans to observe the environment of old age homes and estimate the values of the service during the field visit. This study also tries to find out the problems of senior citizens within the care homes and impact of public policies to solve these issues. Some researchers studied about the elderly issues and did not find out the accurate solutions. Here researcher enthusiasts to conduct an in-depth study about senior citizens policies of Odisha and conditions of elderly in old age homes.

Review of Literatures

Akshaya Kumar Panigrahi (2009) presented a paper titled “Determinants of Living Arrangements of Elderly in Odisha for examining the conditions of senior citizens within the society. The study also focussed to find out the economic conditions of senior citizens and evaluation of different elderly welfare policies. This paper discussed about the impact of socio-economic changes and high living standards leads to elderly loneliness in Odisha. Author suggested that effective elderly policies and public awareness could minimize or eradicate the senior citizen’s loneliness. The study also suggested that lack of financial assistance and housing policies could increase the elderly issues.

Shamsi Akbar, S.C. Tiwari and et al. (2014) in their study titled “Reasons for Living of Elderly in Old Age Homes: An Exploratory Study” tried to inform the causes of living in old age homes. The study resulted that negligence of children, economic insufficiency are prime causes of elderly shifting into care homes. Authors discussed that to live a stress free life and emotional wellbeing the elderly prefer to old age homes. The study also suggested the old age homes should provide emotional supports, qualitative services and elderly friendly environment for senior citizens.

Brajballav Kar conducted a study of “Factors affecting quality of life of older persons- A Qualitative Study from Bhubaneswar, India (2017) to find out the effectiveness of national and state public policies for goodness of senior citizens. The study focused to how senior citizens policy increases the values and dignity of older persons in our society. Author tried to examine how senior citizens policies

ensure the elderly self dependency and standard of living. Author suggested that government of Odisha should enhance the financial assistance towards elderly welfare policies.

Ipsita Mohapatra and Arup Mahapatra (2019) conducted a study titled “Awareness about Social Security Schemes among Elderly: A Comparative Study among Rural and Urban Population of Khordha District, Odisha”. This community-based cross-sectional study administered amongst the rural and urban senior citizens of the field practice area of a medical college. The aims of this study were to examine the awareness about different elderly policies and these utilizations. The paper also tries to explore the challenges faced by both rural and urban elderly of study districts and make a comparative analysis. The study focused on many elderly welfare schemes like Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana, Employee Provident Fund (EPF), Disable Pension and Employees State Insurance Schemes (ESIC) and Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme (IGNOAPS).

Sanghamitra Mohanty (2024) conducted a study of “Rights of Parents and Senior Citizens under Law of Maintenance and Welfare in India” where she stated that, to increase the standard of life and personal dignity the government of Odisha has been launched comprehensive senior citizens policies and plans. Author revealed that in Odisha children cannot take responsibility of their parents and they are accountable for the elderly harassment and loneliness. Study resulted that most of elderly neither live peacefully in their own homes nor in care homes also. Here author reviewed the Maintenance and Welfare of Parents Act 2007 and its effectiveness. The study also referred that elderly should be conscious about their rights and their justice themselves.

Research Methodology

This study is a part of the Ph.D. study titled “Public Policy of State of Odisha and Care of Senior Citizens: A Case Study of Old Age Homes in Puri District”. To find out the objectives of the study researcher conducted a field work. In field visit researcher met 120 elderly inmates from 8 old age homes of 6 blocks, namely Delang, Kanas, Nimapara, Pipili, Puri Sadar and Satyabadi in Puri District. The selected old age homes are aided by central government scheme Integrated Programme for Older People (IPOP) - 1992. This study selected 15 respondents from each old age homes among 120 senior citizens. The study is based on random sampling method where each respondent has an equal priority to give their consents. The selected elderly inmates were from age groups between 60 years and above. Including respondents were staying in old age homes or more, able to understand, reply questions and given written informed consent. Exclusion criteria of data collection were the respondents of non cooperative, physical unsound (e.g. Problem in Speech, Hearing and Vision). The researcher conducted field study through participant observations, focus group discussions and open ended questionnaire to explore the conditions

of senior citizens in old age homes and execution of senior citizens policy in old age homes.

Objectives of the Study

1. To estimate and interpret the senior citizens policies of Odisha.
2. To make a situation analysis of the condition of senior citizens in old age homes in the study district.
3. To evaluate the practices followed by the old age homes, the challenges faced by them in ensuring adequate care.
4. To make a gap analysis between elderly care policies and practices in old age homes.
5. To suggest some new strategies for inclusions.

Estimation of Existing Senior Citizens Policies of Odisha

Different Centrally Sponsored Senior Citizens Policies Administered by Government of Odisha

National Policy of Older Persons (NPOP), Pradhan Mantri Vaya Vandana Yojana (PMVVY), Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme (IGNOAPS), Rashtriya Vayoshri Yojna (RVY), Pradhan Mantri Vaya Vandana Yojana (PMVVY), National Pension Scheme (NPS), Ayushman Bharat Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (AB PM JAY), National Programme for Health Care of Elderly, Senior Citizens Health Insurance Schemes, Integrated Programme for Older Persons, National Action Plan for Senior Citizens, Senior Citizens Saving Schemes (SCSS) Income Tax Rebates, Various Concessions and Facilities, Recreation Centre for Senior Citizens, Senior Citizens Welfare Fund, National Council for Older Persons, Vayoshreshtha Sanman, National Social Assistance Programme (NSAP) and etc.

State Policies of Odisha towards Welfare of Senior Citizens

To provide food security, healthy food supply and nutrition to the Senior citizen of Odisha the government started Emergency Feeding Programme. In 1995 programme started in KBK District like, Rayagada, Malkangiri, Nabarangpur, Balangir, Sonapur, Nupada and Kalahandi District of Odisha. Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizen Act were launched by government of Odisha in the year 2007 to provide proper care, maintenance and welfare of senior citizen in Odisha. The policy suggested that children must take properly care of their older parents and it suggested that senior citizen's contributions are precious for the society and next generations. It decided to run old age home and gave permission to NGO for establishing it properly. Madhubabu Pension Yojan was launched in January 2008 in Odisha. It was inaugurated by chief minister Mr Naveen Patnaik. This policy executed by Department of Social Security and Empowerment of Person with Disability. This policy is applicable for senior citizen

and they must be permanent resident of Odisha. As Per the policy every pension holder must not be involved in any criminal cases and they must be come under the BPL category. The pension holder's annual income should not be more than 24,000 per annum. This policy cleared that the pension holder must not be getting pension from the central or the state government. In every month the senior citizens of Odisha can receive their pension from the office o the Gram Panchayat. National Programme for the Health Care for the Elderly (NPHCE) was launched in 2010 and sponsored by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. This policy aims that there should constructed 10 bedded geriatric wards at District Hospitals. In Odisha Physiotherapy centres are established in the District Health Care Centre and Block Community Health Care Centre. It provides training to the medical officers for health prosperity of senior citizens. To provide safety, right to life and security of senior citizens the government of Odisha established Senior Citizen Security Cell (SCSC) in the year 2012. This Cell creates in urban District of Khordha (Bhubaneswar) and Cuttack. Sub-Inspector of Police is heading to this Cell and one constable should select here to assist him. This cell should investigate and interact with the senior citizen those are victim and beg help. Odisha State Senior Citizen Policy was launched in 2016 in accordance with the National Policy of Senior Citizen 2011. This policy provides a healthy, wealthy and peaceful life to the senior citizens of Odisha. The policy provides health care, social support and stress free life to the elderly of both rural and urban areas. This policy provides benefits to the oldest old, disables and women senior citizens in Odisha with a special care. It promotes partnership across Public Departments, Urban and Local Bodies, Corporate sectors, Academic Institutions, Non-Governmental Organizations and national and international institution. This policy also advised that there have to set up tribunal for the senior citizen those are neglected and tortured by their children. Government of Odisha launched Varistha Nagarika Tirthayatra Yojana in collaboration with IRCTC to provide religious tour to the senior citizens. This policy was enacted in Odisha in the year 2018 for holiest purpose and make reality to a philanthropic ideology. As per this policy the senior citizens can visit different religious destination within the country. Policy suggested that each train can carry the elderly passengers between the numbers of 30 to 1000. As per the guidelines of this policy is there have to a provision to escort officers and medical officers will journey with the tourist. As per this policy tourism department can select 970 pilgrims for the each journey. Criteria of this policy are the applicant must be over 60 years of age and within 75 years of age. This religious tour facilities applicable for poor senior citizen and they must have antodaya card, ration card, widow pension card, MGNREG job card etc. To apply for this tourism facility the senior citizens can apply the form in annexure I and annexure II.

Result

Each old age homes of the study district carried 25 inmates of both male and female. The researcher conducted interview with 120 respondents. Some elderly inmates provided positive opinion regarding the old age homes. They stated that, care homes made them happy and stress free. Some revealed about poor food supply, rude behaviour of caretakers and drinking water troubles. Majority of respondents complained about unhygienic conditions of toilets and bathrooms. Elderly women respondents revealed that, both male and female was not provided separate bedrooms. Half of respondents complained about the poor health services provided by these care homes. Some respondents did not connect with pension policies. Some respondents did not have any health card and other cards. Majority of elderly kept contact with their family members and relatives. Most of respondents affected in high blood pressure and diabetics. Joint pain was very common health issues in majority of elderly women inmates. Interview resulted that inadequate financial assistance is major problem for care homes. There are few numbers of senior citizens policies implemented separately by government of Odisha.

Suggestions

To provide a healthy and secure life to senior citizens government of odisha should implement independent state policies. Government of India also provide financial assistance for welfare of elderly populations. Government of Odisha should increase the financial aid of old age homes. Old age homes should provide standardize services like healthy food supply, sufficient water supply, recreational activities, health check up facilities, well furnished rooms and other benefits. Care takers should compassionate towards the inmates. Social awareness programme and realizations of children about the values of elderly parents could lead to their happiness.

Conclusion

In rural areas majority of senior citizens are uneducated than the urban areas. Senior citizens have not any pension facilities and saving benefits, therefore they are dependable on their children in financially. In Odisha urban senior citizens are facing different types of issues like murder, kidnap and theft etc. Due to property disputes between older parents and children the senior citizens are abandoned from their own house. Some children are providing physical and mental torture to their own old parents, this type of incidents take place in daily news paper of Odisha. The legislative framework and judicial activism are reached in dormant stage in Odisha in case of senior citizen.

References

1. Akbar Shamsi, Tiwari S.C. and et al, 2014, Reasons for Living of Elderly in Old Age Homes: An Exploratory Study, The International Journal of Indian Psychology, Volume 2, Issue 1, pp 55-61.

2. Amiri Mohammad, July-September, 2018, Problem Faced by Old Age People, The International Journal of Indian Psychology, Punjab University, Chandigarh, India, Volume 6, Issue 3.
3. Dash Anjali, November 2013, Health Care Policy and Programme in India and Odisha (A Historical Prospect Analysis), Zenith International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, ISSN 2231-5780, Volume 3, pp.103-115.
4. Dr. Rath Namita, Biswal Prasanta Kumar and Panda Susen Kumar, 2017, Care Facilities of Elderly People in Odisha, Journal of Geriatric Care and Research, Volume 4, No 1, pp.1-3.
5. Kar Brajaballav, 2017, Factors Affecting Quality of Life of Older Persons- A Qualitative Study from Bhubaneswar, India, Journal of Geriatric Care and Research, Volume 4, Number 2, pp. 47-54.
6. Mishra Abhisek, 2 June 2007, Health Profile of Elderly in Urban Slums of Cuttack City, Odisha, International Journal of Biomedical and Advance Research, Volume 8, Issue 5, pp. 217-221. Available At- <https://doi.org/10.7439/ijbar>
7. Mohanty Sanghamitra, 2024, Rights of Parents and Senior Citizens under Law of Maintenance and Welfare in India, International Journal of Research Culture Society, Volume 8, Issue 3.
8. Mohaptra Ipsita and Mahapatra Arup, 2019 Awareness about Social Security Schemes among Elderly: A Comparative Study among Rural and Urban Population of Khordha District, Odisha, National Journal of Indian Association of Preventive and Social Medicine, Volume 31, Issue 2.
9. Panigrahi Akshaya, 2009, Determinants of Living Arrangements of Elderly in Orissa: An Analysis, The Institute for Social and Economic Change, Bangalore, ISBN 81-7791-184-8.
